

TR-CHECK LIST INSPECTION FORM

Evaluated Application: _____ Evaluator: _____

GROUP 01: PEOPLE AND ACTORS

Existence and Quality of Information

Question	Sufficient	Insufficient	Nonexistent
Information about the actors, such as name, address, phone number, email, and the person responsible for the organization?			
Information indicating which data protection authorities regulate the use of personal data by the actors?			
Information about the role (function) of each actor in the use of personal data?			

Presentation Format

Question	Appropriate	Inappropriate	Improvements
Design elements (texts, figures, images, etc.) used to present information about the actors.			
Simplicity, objectivity, and relevance of the information to effectively support the analysis of actors involved in the use of personal data.			
Ease of access to information so that the individual is not required to perform complex searches or analyze/read large volumes of text.			
The available information eliminates the need for the individual to seek information from other sources.			

GROUP 02: PURPOSE OF USE

Existence and Quality of Information

Question	Sufficient	Insufficient	Nonexistent
Description of the purpose of personal data use.			
Information about the law/regulation that makes the use of personal data lawful.			
Information on which personal data will be used to achieve the stated purposes.			
Identification of the legally responsible actor for the use of personal data.			
Information on whether personal data processing is carried out exclusively by automated means, without human oversight.			
Information on the duration of personal data processing for the stated purpose.			

Presentation Format

Question	Appropriate	Inappropriate	Improvements
Design elements (texts, figures, images, etc.) used to present information about the purpose(s) of data use.			
Simplicity, objectivity, and relevance of the information to effectively support the analysis of the purpose(s) of personal data use.			
Ease of access to information so that the individual is not required to perform complex searches or read large volumes of text.			
The available information eliminates the need for users to seek information from other sources.			

GROUP 03: PERSONAL DATA

Existence and Quality of Information

Question	Sufficient	Insufficient	Nonexistent
Information on which personal data are used.			
Description of how personal data are structured (details that better explain the data).			
Information about the origin of the data (devices, third-party acquisition, sharing, etc.).			
In cases where data provision is mandatory, information about what may occur if the data are not provided.			
Information about the purpose of using personal data and how (which process) the data are handled.			
Information about the consent granted by the individual for the use of personal data.			

Presentation Format

Question	Appropriate	Inappropriate	Improvements
Design elements (texts, figures, images, etc.) used to present information about processed personal data.			
Simplicity, objectivity, and relevance of the information to effectively support the analysis of the purpose of personal data use.			
Ease of access to information so that the individual is not required to perform complex searches or read large volumes of text.			
The available information eliminates the need for users to seek information from other sources.			

GROUP 04: TRANSFER AND SHARING

Existence and Quality of Information

Question	Sufficient	Insufficient	Nonexistent
Information on which personal data are transferred or shared with third parties.			
Information about the purpose of the transfer and/or sharing of personal data.			
Information about the legal basis (law/regulation) ensuring the legality of data sharing.			
Complete details of the data recipient, enabling identification and contact.			
Details of the organization that monitors the use of personal data in the recipient's country or region, enabling identification and contact.			
Specification of which data were transferred or shared and how they were obtained.			
Information to recall how consent for data sharing was provided and/or authorized.			
Information about events that trigger the transfer/sharing of personal data.			

Presentation Format

Question	Appropriate	Inappropriate	Improvements
Design elements (texts, figures, images, etc.) used to present information about data transfer/sharing.			
Simplicity, objectivity, and relevance of the information to effectively support the analysis of data transfer/sharing.			
Ease of access to information so that the individual is not required to perform complex searches or read large volumes of text.			
The available information eliminates the need for users to seek information from other sources.			

GROUP 05: AGENCY AND NEGOTIABILITY

Existence and Quality of Information

Question	Sufficient	Insufficient	Nonexistent
Information on how the individual can request a copy of their data, modify consent for data use, file a complaint, or exercise any rights regarding their data.			
Information on contact channels (phone numbers, emails) of actors involved in the use of personal data.			
Information and/or features that allow the individual to request a copy of their data, modify consent, file a complaint, or exercise rights directly within the software, without the need to initiate external contact.			

Presentation Format

Question	Appropriate	Inappropriate	Improvements
Design elements (texts, figures, images, etc.) used to present information about regulatory bodies and actions to question or verify the use of data.			
Simplicity, objectivity, and relevance of the information to effectively support the analysis of regulatory bodies and user actions.			
Ease of access to information so that the individual is not required to perform complex searches or read large volumes of text.			
The available information eliminates the need for users to seek information from other sources.			